

Case Study

Transverse Myelitis: A Rare Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Transverse myelitis is defined by inflammation in the spinal cord and has clinical symptoms in the form of neurological dysfunction in autonomic, sensory, and motor pathways, as a result of the channel passing the rostral border of inflammation. Acute Transverse myelitis may be a rare syndrome. A 16-year male patient was admitted with the main complaint that his hand grip had deteriorated over the previous two days, a challenge while mixing meals. On Examination the patient and his vitals were found to be stable but strength of distal part of upper limbs was 1/5 and lower limbs was 5/5. MRI cervical spine with a screening of the whole spine was found to be long segment fusiform thickening of the cervical cord extending from C3 to the superior endplate of D1. He was treated with methyl prednisolone 1gm, IV and other symptomatic and supportive treatment and 80% improvement in the hand grip was noticed.

INTRODUCTION

Transverse myelitis is defined by inflammation in the spinal cord and has clinical symptoms in the form of neurological dysfunction in autonomic, sensory, and motor pathways, as a result of the channel passing the rostral border of inflammation. When no compressive lesion is present, transverse myelitis manifests as a localized inflammation along one or more spinal cord levels. The myelin that protects nerve cells can be damaged by this inflammation, which can

lead to neurological dysfunction such as weakness, sensory abnormalities, and issues with the bowel and bladder [1]. With an annual frequency of one to eight new cases per million people, Acute Transverse myelitis may be a rare syndrome. MRI scans and lumbar punctures frequently revealed sensory complaints as well as signs of acute inflammation [2]. The first-line treatment for transverse myelitis is glucocorticoids. Additional treatments include plasmapheresis, IVIG Therapy,

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Immunosuppressant. Treatment with steroids or other drugs doesn't cure transverse myelitis, but it might relieve symptoms. Some patients may recover fully, while others might have minor or more serious long-term problem.

CASE REPORT:

A 16-year male patient was admitted with the main complaint that his hand grip had deteriorated over the previous two days, a challenge while mixing meals. The patient appeared to be symptom-free two days prior, and the fever history was denied. He had no difficulties lifting hands above the head, and he denied having loose stools. There have never been any prior complaints of this nature. No prior history of medication use. No family history of symptoms resembling these. On Examination the patient and his vitals were found to be stable but both hand grips were found to be less than 10%. So, the physician suspected him of transverse myelitis and advised him to electro neuro myography finding, an MRI cervical spine with a screening of the whole spine, ECG, urea, and total bilirubin levels. Here electro neuro myography findings were normal upper and lower limb nerve conduction studies, MRI cervical spine with a screening of the whole spine was found to be long segment fusiform thickening of the cervical cord extending from C3 to the superior endplate of D1, which shows a long segment central hyperintense intramedullary signal involving both halves of the cord and no central canal dilatation as shown in the figure 1, ECG shows sinus tachycardia, inferior infarction. The regular examination of plantar reflexes and power was found to be as follows in Tab: 1, 2, 3. On day 9 the hand grip was found to be 80% this shows that the patient's condition was improved with the treatment provided in Tab: 4.

Fig 1: MRI SPINE SHOWING TRANSVERSE MYELITIS

Table 1: Plantar reflexes

Plantar Reflexes	Day-1		Day-3		Day-5	
	Right	Left	Right	Left	Right	Left
Biceps	1	1	1	1	1	1
Triceps	1	1	1	1	1	1
Supinator	1	1	1	1	1	1
Knee	1	1	2	2	3	3
Ankle	0	0	0	0	3	3

Table 2: On Day 2 power was found to be

Upper limb	Right	Left
Proximal	5/5	5/5
Distal	1/5	1/5
Lower limb		
Proximal	5/5	5/5
Distal	5/5	5/5

Table 3: On Day 3 power of limb was found to be

Upper limb	Right	Left
Deltoid	5/5	5/5
Biceps	5/5	5/5
Triceps	5/5	5/5
Brachioradialis	5/5	5/5
Wrist extension	5/5	5/5
Wrist flexion	5/5	5/5
Thumb extension	2/5	3/5
Finger extension	2/5	3/5
Finger flexion	2/5	3/5
Lower limb		
Proximal	5/5	5/5
Distal	5/5	5/5

Table 4: Treatment provided during therapy

Drug Prescribed	Generic Name	Dose	Frequency	Route of Administration
Inj. Pantop	pantoprazole	40 mg	OD	IV
Inj. Ondansetron	Ondansetron	40mg	BD	IV
Inj optineuron	Thiamine	1 Ampule in 1 pint DNS	OD	IV
Tab. MVT	Multivitamin		BD	IV
Inj.Zofer	Ondansetron	4mg	BD	IV
Inj. Methyl Prednisolone	Methyl Prednisolone	1g	OD	IV
T. Prednisolone	Prednisolone	40mg	OD	Oral

DISCUSSION

In our case a 16-year old male patient was admitted with the main complaint that his hand grip had deteriorated. People between the ages of 10 to 19 and 30 to 39 are considered to have a greater incidence rate than other age groups. [3] Patient faced challenge while mixing meals. On physical examination strength of distal part of upper limb was 1/5 and lower limb was 5/5, plantar reflexes and power was found to be as in Tab: 1, 2, 3. the patient appeared to be symptom-free two days prior, and the fever history was denied. He had no difficulties in lifting his hands above the heads, and he denied having loose stools. He had never been any prior complaints of this nature. No prior history of medication use. No family history of symptoms resembling these. Symptoms include motor, sensory, and/or autonomic dysfunction. Rapidly, increasing paraparesis, which can affect the upper extremities at first with flaccidity and then spasticity, is one type of motor impairment. Motor symptoms may vary depending on the level of the spinal cord involved. White matter structures in the spinal cord may have been harmed, which would explain this. At the level involved, symptoms like pain, dysesthesia, and paraesthesia are most frequently accompanied by sensory involvement. Urinary urgency, bladder/bowel incontinence, difficulty or inability to void, bowel constipation, or sexual dysfunction are examples of autonomic symptoms of TM. The initial indicator of myelitis may be urinary retention, which calls for additional research into myelopathy Upper cervical lesions (C1-C5) may affect all four extremities. [4] According to the guidelines of the Transverse Myelitis Consortium

Working Group, diagnosing TM involves validating the clinical presentation of spinal cord symptoms through contrast-enhanced spinal cord MRI or detecting elevated protein levels in the CSF. Examining patients with TM may benefit greatly from electrophysiological studies. Electromyography (EMG) and nerve conduction investigations can identify and characterise any peripheral neurological pathology, whose exclusion would provide strong evidence in favour of a spinal cord process [5]. Additionally, spinal cord compression should be excluded through spinal MRI, and brain lesions ruled out via brain MRI, mirroring our case where we conducted MRI for TM exclusion. [5] On day 9 the hand grip was found to be 80% this shows that the patient's condition was improved with the treatment provided in Tab: 4. The three major treatments for TM are high dosage intravenous methylprednisolone (IVMP), plasma exchange, and/or intravenous cyclophosphamide.[6] When a robust clinical suspicion arises, prompt administration of treatment is crucial. The recommended courses involve methylprednisolone (30 mg/kg, capped at 1000 mg daily) or dexamethasone (120 to 200 mg daily for adults) over a span of three to five days .[7]

CONCLUSION

As transverse myelitis is defined by inflammation in the spinal cord improvement in patient condition was seen after prescribing a systemic corticosteroid (Inj. Methylprednisolone). The diagnosis is supported by the patient's medical history, a neurological examination, and supporting tests such an MRI and CSF analysis.

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